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**TIL, TA'LIM, TARJIMA
XALQARO JURNALI**

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TIL O'RGANISH VA UNING MOHIYATI XUSUSIDA

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada o'quvchining ikkinchi til xususiyatlarini o'zlashtirish bosqichlari haqida umumiy tasavvurga ega bo'lmasa, o'quvchi tilining ba'zi xususiyatlari kutilmagan bo'lishi haqida fikrlar yoritilgan. Ikkinchi til bo'yicha maqolamizda natijalarini taqdim etar ekanmiz, biz maqsadli tilga oid bir qancha misollar, maqsadli tilni tahlil qilishni mashq qilish imkoniyatini berish uchun qo'shimcha namunalarni kiritdik. Albatta, o'qituvchilar doimo talabalarning tilini tahlil qiladilar. Ular o'quvchilar o'zlariga o'rgatilgan narsalarni o'rgangan-o'rganmaganligini va ularning tillari maqsadli tilga qanchalik mos kelishini aniqlashga harakat qiladilar. Ammo taraqqiyotni har doim ham bu shartlar bilan o'lchab bo'lmaydi. Ba'zida tilni o'zlashtirish qisman yodlash yoki o'rganishga asoslangan to'g'ri shakldan foydalanishning kamayishi bilan namoyon bo'ladi. Biz ularning tildan foydalanishini kuzatmoqdamiz, lekin biz ularga kuzatilgan tildan foydalanish ortidagi bilimlar haqida ko'proq ma'lumot olishga yordam berish yo'llarini ishlab chiqmoqdamiz. Talabaning hozirgi til bilimi tizimli narsami yoki oddiy xulq-atvor orqali oddiy mahsulot sifatida o'rganilgan alohida elementmi, buni aniqlash qiyinligi haqidagi g'oyalar ilgari suriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: hozirgi til, tizimli o'rganish, ikkinchi til, o'zlashtirish, yondashuv, muloqot, muvaffaqiyatli, o'qituvchilar ehtiyoji, ona tili, chalkashlik.

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О ИЗУЧЕНИИ ЯЗЫКА И СУЩНОСТЬ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье утверждается, что некоторые особенности языка учащегося могут быть довольно неожиданными, если не иметь общего представления об этапах приобретения учащимися особенностей второго языка. Представляя результаты нашего исследования второго языка, мы включили ряд примеров изучаемого языка и дополнительные образцы, чтобы дать вам возможность попрактиковаться в анализе изучаемого языка. Конечно, учителя всегда анализируют язык учеников. Они пытаются определить, усвоили ли учащиеся то, чему их учили, и насколько хорошо их язык соответствует целевому языку. Но прогресс не всегда может быть измерен в этих терминах. Иногда овладение языком проявляется в снижении использования правильной формы, частично основанной на запоминании или обучении. Мы наблюдаем за их использованием языка, но мы разрабатываем способы помочь им узнать больше о знаниях, лежащих в основе их наблюдаемого использования языка. Выдвигаются идеи о том, что трудно определить, является ли текущее языковое знание учащегося систематической вещью или отдельным элементом, усвоенным как простое произведение через простое поведение.

Ключевые слова: текущий язык, систематическое изучение, второй язык, овладение, подход, общение, успешно, носитель языка, путаница.

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ABOUT LANGUAGE LEARNING AND ITS ESSENCE

ABSTRACT

This article argues that some features of a learner's language can be quite surprising if one does not have a general idea of the stages of acquisition of second language features by learners. As we present our second language research findings, we have included a number of learner language examples and additional samples to give you a chance to practice analyzing learner language. Of course, teachers always analyze students' language. They try to determine whether the learners have learned what they have been taught and how well their language matches the target language. But progress cannot always be measured in these terms. Sometimes language acquisition is manifested in a decline in the use of the correct form, based partly on memorization or learning. We observe their use of language, but we develop ways to help them learn more about the knowledge underlying their observable use of language. The ideas are put forward that it is difficult to determine whether the student's current language knowledge is a systematic thing or a separate element learned as a simple piece through simple behavior.

Keywords: current language, systematic learning, second language, acquisition, approach, communicate, successfully, native speaker, confusion.

Knowing more about the development of learner language helps teachers to assess teaching procedures in the light of what they can reasonably expect to accomplish in the classroom. As we will see, some characteristics of learner language can be quite perplexing if one does not have an overall picture of the steps learners go through in acquiring features of the second language. In presenting some of the findings of second language research, we have included a number of examples of learner language as well as some additional samples to give you an opportunity to practice analyzing learner language. Of course, teachers analyze learner language all the time. They try to determine whether students have learned what has been taught and how closely their language matches the target language. But progress cannot always be measured in these terms. Sometimes language acquisition is reflected in a decrease in the use of a correct form that was based on rote memorization or chunk learning. New errors may be based on an emerging ability to extend a particular grammatical form beyond the specific items with which it was first learned. In this sense, an increase in error may be an indication of progress. For example, like first language learners, second language learners usually learn the irregular past tense forms of certain common verbs before they learn to apply

the regular simple past -ed marker. That means that a learner who says 'I buyed a bus ticket' may know more about English grammar than one who says 'I bought a bus ticket'. The one who says 'buyed' knows a rule for forming the past tense and has applied it to an irregular verb. Without further information, we cannot conclude that the one who says 'bought' would use the regular past -ed marker where it is appropriate, but the learner who says 'buyed' has provided evidence of developing knowledge of a systematic aspect of English. Teachers and researchers cannot read learners' minds, so they must infer what learners know by observing what they do. We observe their spontaneous language use, but we also design procedures that help to reveal more about the knowledge underlying their observable use of language. Without these procedures, it is often difficult to determine whether a particular behavior is representative of something systematic in a learner current language knowledge or simply an isolated item, learned as a chunk. Like first language learners, second language learners do not learn language simply through imitation and practice. They produce sentences that are not exactly like those they have heard. These new sentences appear to be based on internal cognitive processes and prior knowledge that interact with the language they hear around them. Both first and second language acquisition are best described as developing systems with their own evolving rules and patterns, not as imperfect versions of the target language.

For instance, grammatical morphemes such as the -ing of the present progressive or the -ed of the simple past are not acquired at the same time, but in sequence. Furthermore, the acquisition of certain grammatical features is similar for children in different environments. As children continue to hear and use their language, they are able to revise these systems so that they increasingly resemble the language spoken in their environment. Are there developmental sequences for second language acquisition? How does the prior knowledge of the first language affect the acquisition of the second (or third) language? How does instruction affect second language acquisition? Are there differences between learners whose only contact with the new language is in a language course and those who use the language in daily life? Until the late 1950s, people tended to see second language learners' speech simply as an incorrect version of the target language. A simplified version would predict that, where differences exist, errors would be bi-directional, that is, for example, French speakers learning English and English speakers learning French would make errors on linguistic features. For example, in English, direct objects, whether nouns or pronouns, come after the verb ('The dog eats the cookie. The dog eats it.'). In French, direct objects that are nouns follow the verb (Le chien mange le biscuit literally, 'The dog eats the cookie'). However, direct object pronouns precede the verb (Le chien le mange literally, 'The dog it eats'). There would be predicted that a native speaker of English might make the error of saying: Le chien mange le when learning French, and that a native speaker of French might say 'The dog it ate' when learning English. In fact, English speakers learning French are more likely to make the predicted error than French speakers learning English. This may be due to the fact that English speakers learning French hear many examples of sentences with subject-verb-object word order (for example, Le chien mange le biscuit) and make the incorrect error based on both the word order of their first language and evidence from the second language—that all direct objects come after the verb. French-speaking learners of English, on the other hand, hearing and seeing no evidence that English direct object pronouns precede verbs, do not tend to use this pattern from their first language. Most learners believe that idiomatic or metaphorical expressions cannot simply be translated word for word. As a result of the finding that many aspects of learners' language could not be explained by the number of researchers began to take a different approach to analyzing learners' errors. This approach, which

developed during the 1970s, became known as 'error analysis' and involved detailed description and analysis of the kinds of errors second language learners make. The goal of this research to discover what learners really know about the language. Both of language and culture have a function of communication because they both carry meanings. On the one hand, language carries syntactic, semantic and pragmatic meanings for language users to communicate. On the other hand, culture carries meanings and cultural meanings are expressed through patterns of behavior. In order to communicate successfully across languages and cultures, one must understand culturally different norms of interaction and people's values and thought. Sometimes linguistic correct sentences could cause misunderstanding or confusion when they are in a different cultural context. Discourse competence is the ability learners have to connect sentences and to form a meaningful whole from a series of utterances. Social-linguistic competence is the knowledge of the social-cultural rules of languages which requires an understanding of the roles of the participants, the information they share, and the function of the interaction. Strategic competence is the strategies that learners use to compensate for imperfect knowledge of rules or the target language, to sustain communication. Technology is a facilitating tool of education which teachers and students get a great deal of benefit from. Today's language teachers need to learn how to take advantage of the technology and how to integrate it into their teaching skills. Computers, smart phones, tablets etc. provide powerful opportunities to learn foreign language. As the use of smart phone, computer etc. is increasingly common among students; teachers need to equip themselves with today's technology. Smart boards can be instrumental in engaging and motivating student in the class. For instance pronunciation though the teacher is not a native speaker can be taught to learners with ease using smart phone/board. Teachers who introduce technology to their students may get a great deal of satisfaction when they accomplish better. Technology doesn't constitute methodology, but teachers utilize technology to complement it. How can teachers begin to integrate technology in language teaching? I think first, teachers need to contemplate their aims pertaining teaching styles. Different technological materials offer different advantages therefore teachers should be aware of utilities technology. Teachers may apply technology to their teaching skills. As a matter of fact, when teachers use technology in class they should know students' current language skills and needs. In a nutshell, the role of technology in teaching foreign language is very significant in foreign language teaching process. We use it with media, shopping, education, communication tools. Similarly, it has made great contribution to language learning process. Undoubtedly, using technology has positive effects on teaching and learning the language. How can technology be applied to enhance teaching/learning the language? When, computer, internet, smart boards, cell phones, video games, music players etc. are used in the target language learning process, students' motivation and language awareness is raised. The new generation (teachers/students) is good at using technology. They are all engaged with technological tools and somehow are involved in the target language through technology. Teaching by using traditional methods is no longer motivating and enjoyable for learners. Learners are more interactive, and learning outcomes bring about efficient results. Moreover, the positive outcomes will lead to satisfaction for both teachers and learners. Experienced teachers present different opportunities to students working at different rates and levels. The most widely used device is smart phone. Teachers and learners use it for developing the skills such as listening, and reading; furthermore, watching target language elements on technological tools enable students to improve their second language proficiency. Today's technology is breaking down all borders and bounds faster than physical terms. Technology tools for communication, collaboration, social networking... In particular, these tools have

transformed how parents and families manage their daily lives and seek out entertainment, how teachers use materials in the classroom with young children and communicate with parents and families, and how we deliver teacher education and professional development. Effective teachers provide a natural learning environment for learners. Most teachers before lessons consider what they are going to teach and what kind of activities they will apply in their lessons. Upon deciding on this, they get ready through making lesson plan and finding the right resources or elements they will use. First of all, technological devices are more interesting for the students to make some useful activities. For example; making online activities with smart board is very enjoyable for the learners. Integrating technology into language teaching and learning will bring about undivided motivation that will lead to achievement. The possibility to use one source to practice different skills facilitates preparing the lesson and is a time-saving solution. Coming back to grammar, the second form of introducing Past Perfect tense to intermediate learners is the use of short movies from reliable teaching English online sources such as engvid.com [www.engvid.com,]. It is a website created by native English speakers and covers, inter alia, grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, TOEFL, and IELTS issues. It is free of charge and one is able to use their materials without signing up. Past Perfect structure and use is explained by a native speaker with the use of a whiteboard. After the short eight-minute movie students can take a quiz to check their understanding. The advantages of its use are obvious: there is a new teacher on the Internet, the movie is appropriate for visual and auditory learners, the quiz may fulfill kinesthetic learners' expectations, and the lessons on these websites are often conducted in a humorous way. Moreover, students have the opportunity to listen to native speakers. However, it is crucial to choose a reliable source of teaching on the Internet, since there is a great number of those which do not serve educational purposes at all. Also, the teacher should consider whether the materials will be a kind of challenge to their level of knowledge and belong to students' interest.

Vocabulary is a crucial factor in learning foreign language since words are basic units needed to communicate. There are several ways one can acquire and practice vocabulary, e.g., through checking words in a dictionary, speaking, or writing. However, the way of introducing vocabulary is different in a course book and on the Internet websites created for teaching language. Usually, in a course book the students' task is to match the words with the objects from the photo. Then, they have to check the answers with the tape. The inductive method applied here is perfect for visual learners but not really suitable for auditory or kinesthetic learners, since they listen to the tape only once and have no opportunity to practice. How does it work with the use of websites? The analyzed vocabulary is connected with objects in bedroom. Again, the website engvid.com serves a short lesson with a native speaker talking about the objects and drawing them on a whiteboard. Again, students have the chance to do a quiz after watching a video. After introducing vocabulary this way, students may play games on different websites, such as British Council web games. The first one serves a matching words with pictures activity, while the second one has different types of board or memory games with questions concerning the vocabulary items. It is based on matching and listening to the words, and ticking the words they have just heard. Not only is it a good opportunity to practice, but it also entertains students. They acquire the language through fun and may forget that they actually learn. The use of technology items, such as a laptop, an interactive whiteboard, and the Internet in itself might be encouraging and entertaining for students since it is different from a classical course book. Moreover, such games are perfect for visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learners, because the games activate all senses: sight, hearing, and touch. Listening is an important skill to develop

during learning in order to understand others in real conversations. Course books usually offer tasks such as filling in the gaps, true or false, or answering questions after listening, while the vocabulary is connected with the topic of the lesson. When it comes to the use of mass media, the radio and TV are perfect tools to develop listening skills. Listening to the real podcasts or watching news is a great opportunity to get to know what is happening in the world. They can also learn culture from native speakers. It can be any podcast or TV news which students are able to understand and will be in their interest. For upper intermediate learners' the BBC radio 1 podcast might work. The website contains podcasts about current affairs as well as British culture. Moreover, the language used there is not artificial, as in course books, but the one spoken every day. Another important advantage is the fact that watching increases students' visual and critical awareness [Tiffani, 2009, p. 83]. Furthermore, choosing a movie, teachers can draw students' attention to the language, while watching with subtitles makes the understanding of the language easier [Tiffani, 2009, p. 88]. After listening to the radio or watching news students may start a discussion based on issues they have just heard to develop speaking skills. Such activity enables them to give their opinions on current affairs, agree or disagree with peers, and look for arguments supporting their views. Speaking, which is an inseparable part of listening skill, can be also conducted through an online chat. It offers a contact with different culture and it is a real communication with a real purpose [Duodena & Hockley, 2008]. Also, it is a good writing practice: students can send messages on chat or even e-mails to their peers. Mass media tools such as newspapers, the radio, and the Internet may serve educational purposes. In cases mentioned above they turn out to be even better than traditional course books. Firstly, they perfectly fulfill different types of learners' needs. Secondly, they encourage students to learn and are a form of entertainment. Those tools make learning more appealing because students may find something of their interest in teaching materials. Due to the need for a quick learning in all higher educational institutions, which was caused by strict quarantine measures, there was an urgent need to introduce learning system that was convenient and understandable for both teachers and students. To date, higher education institutions conducted learning, which provided a correspondence education. Therefore, when there was a sharp need for education, in a number of universities there was no experience in organizing such work and no unified system of teacher training, as well as there was no single methodological approach. This led to the need for teachers to individually study and put into practice various electronic learning services. The analysis of various electronic learning services showed the presence of a large number of existing platforms for different target audiences (Moodle, ISPRING, Google, etc.). Among these platforms for teaching students in our conditions, resources on Google were chosen as sufficiently clear and convenient for quick mastering. These resources would be helpful for educational institution for teachers and students. The choice was based on the prevalence of the system, convenient support for different content, the ability to create the content of "original test items", user management, reporting system. Another important selection criterion was free of charge, technical readiness and the ability of students to connect to this system and the availability of educational video materials for quick preparation of content by the teachers themselves. The quick development of the Classroom for teachers was facilitated by the simple settings and integration of the Google Classroom with Google Drive, Documents, Forms, and an e-mail, as well as ease of placement, the ability to share information and materials for training on the tasks page. It also became convenient for the teacher that it is possible to test the knowledge of students of the entire group simultaneously and post individual tasks for each student.

The question is what must the instructor know in order to use computer-assisted technologies more effectively particularly in the classroom? Use of the numerous Internet resources presumes sufficient hardware expertise on the part of the instructor to actively participate. Language instructors at any level of education should thoroughly consider the potential of available technology-assisted resources and web-based language materials. In order to do that, the instructor has to relate their chosen teaching methodologies to the various Internet resources and other computer-assisted teaching tools. To proceed in such an endeavor, the instructor should be familiar with the most popular information-search engines on the World Wide Web. They must know methods of information retrieval and must have the skills to explore hyperlinks for the best suited multimedia assistance useful in each specific language learning activity. The questions are then how to integrate these new technologies into our daily teaching of foreign languages, how to build our lessons. Incorporating specific resources in classroom activities, and what online activities would be helpful in each student's pursuit of their chosen foreign language. This section will first trace the history of language learning methodologies and the role of technology. It will show the relationship between them in terms of theories, choices, and objectives. The history of connecting foreign language acquisition with technology and multimedia tools in the educational process represents a certain duality. On the one hand, after being incorporated into the process of foreign language acquisition, multimedia tools influence how language is taught. On the other hand, learning objectives and goals in the foreign language acquisition process influence how technology, particularly computers and the Internet, will be adapted for the educational process. Many scientists consider these changes not simply as "a polar shift from structural to communicative perspectives," but as "a more complex overlapping of three theoretical movements structural, cognitive, and socio cognitive". Lots of experience in the language acquisition process demonstrates that using technology as a tool in the learning process brings a noticeable improvement in students' foreign language competency. Audio and visual technology has a significant impact by providing foreign language instructors with a support tool that brings higher quality, real-life learning experiences from the world into the classroom. Using video instruction adds visual and auditory stimuli to language learning. Authentic video stories became useful. Video integrated into a course storyline or created for communicative situations extends and enriches the listening process by supporting student perceptions with facial expressions, body language, intonation, and the rhythm of the language. However, there should be some technical difficulties in the preparation of training material among teachers, since the reference materials on creating forms for teachers on Google would not provided in full volume, which led to the loss of part of the prepared data and to the loss of time. Also, during the learning the language, the requirements for the students themselves also increase: they must be more informed and disciplined, learn to assimilate and generalize the information received from various sources independently (video lectures, books, teaching aids, recommendations, various information sites on the subject under the study, etc.). During the summarizing the lessons using the various remote control forms, where there is a solution to practical problems of different difficulty levels: test situational cases, solving more complex multilevel problems to compare or deny any facts and others, the student reveals his weaknesses in the preparation of theoretical material. A second language learner is different from a very young child acquiring a first language. This is true in terms of both the learner characteristics and the environments in which first and second language acquisition typically occur. Think about how the characteristics and learning conditions of the following learners may differ: (1) a young child learning a first language; (2) a child learning a second language in day care or on the playground; (3) adolescents

taking a foreign language class in their own count y; (4) an adult immigrant with limited or disrupted education working in a second language environment and having no opportunity to go to language classes. By definition, all second language learners, regardless of age, have already acquired at least one language. This prior knowledge may be an advantage in the sense that they have an idea of how languages work. On the other hand, knowledge of other languages can lead learners to make incorrect guesses about how the second language works, and this may result in errors that first language learners would not make. Very young language learners begin the task of first language acquisition without the cognitive maturity or metalinguistic awareness that older second language learners have. Although young second language learners have begun to develop these characteristics, they will still have far to go in these areas, as well as in the area of world knowledge, before they reach the levels already attained by adults and adolescents. On the one hand, cognitive maturity and metalinguistic awareness allow older learners to solve problems and engage in discussions about language. And when identifying its weaknesses in knowledge, the student must consciously work on the errors, returning to the repetition and understanding of the theoretical part of the material that he poorly prepared, that not every student understands or is ready to fulfill. Also, by watching English news or TV series, and reading newspapers, students can learn English culture. However, the most important advantage of teaching foreign language through mass media is the contact with an authentic language. The ability to listen to native speakers may facilitate own performance and understanding. However, there are also disadvantages of its use. Firstly, there is no curriculum. Consequently, the whole class preparation is in teachers' hands. Secondly, mass media tools do not always explain rules of the language usage, course books do. For those who prefer deductive way of learning, studying only with mass media might turn out to be problematic. Also, it is not always possible to find a reliable source appropriate to learners' level. Nevertheless, it is worth introducing at least some of mass media elements to lessons to facilitate both teaching and learning. Learners, in an informal second language-learning environment, are usually allowed to be silent until they are ready to speak may also have opportunities to practice their second language 'voice' in songs and games that allow them to blend their voices. Learners are often forced to speak-to meet the requirements of a classroom or to carry out everyday tasks such as shopping, medical visits, or job interviews. Young children in informal settings are usually exposed to the second language for many hours every day. Older learners, especially students in language classrooms, are more likely to receive only limited exposure to the second language. Classroom learners not only spend less time in contact the language, they also tend to be. For example, classroom learners are often taught that is somewhat formal in comparison to the language as it is social settings.

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